

**X-Mansion
University**

Draw 1 extra card
when you play
a shared project

**Hogwarts
University**

Each 2 shared
project, you
gain 3 points

**Miskatonic
University**

You can publish
2 papers in a your
non-shared project

Stark University

Each 2 non-
shared projects
draw a card and
gain 2 points

Stark University

Each 2 non-
shared projects
draw a card and
gain 2 points

Universities
(print per 2)

**X-Mansion
University**

Draw 1 extra card
when you play
a shared project

**Hogwarts
University**

Each 2 shared
project, you
gain 3 points

**Miskatonic
University**

You can publish
2 papers in a your
non-shared project